

Title: Bitcoin, Bitcoin Cash, Bitcoin Gold, Bitcoin Candy, why so many forks?

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INTRODUCTION:

Bitcoin is first cryptocurrency that proved blockchain's unlimited capabilities. This is without a doubt, a paradigm shift for a decentralized economy. However, it doesn't go without its problems with a democratized process to handle protocol improvements.

AIM:

Explain the differences between Bitcoin, Bitcoin Cash, Bitcoin Gold, Bitcoin Candy and possibly more upcoming forks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

What happens when a fork is proposed? Discuss the process during the fork and the result it generates such as additional market capitalization to the overall cryptocurrency economy.

RESULTS:

Different Bitcoin chains produce different rules for utility, scaling, mining and growth.

CONCLUSIONS:

The forks and spawning of many Bitcoin chains are working exactly to the power of decentralization. This is commonly seen as a negative impact. However, we should be embracing this characteristic of a decentralized blockchain.

KEYWORDS:

Bitcoin, Bitcoin Cash, Bitcoin Gold, Bitcoin Candy, Blockchain, Decentralization, Cryptocurrency, Economics, Mining, Scaling,

BIOGRAPHY:

Wayne is an early adopter of Bitcoin, Blockchain and Cryptocurrencies. He is the Co-founder of Assembly Block, specializing in development and advisory in the blockchain space. Wayne has significant blockchain and cryptocurrency experience, having previously held the position of Senior Product Manager at Mogo and Senior Director, Head of Product at nTrust, where he designed and developed a Bitcoin wallet and exchange.

Wayne comes from a UX, Design and Product background having worked in the gaming industry for 7+ years. In his early career, he was a Designer and Producer at Electronic Arts working on many AAA titles such as FIFA, The Sims 2, and EA Sports Active. Wayne also mentors at Vancouver Film School and is part of the VanUE (Vancouver User Experience Group) Organizing Committee to connect young UX design professionals with the industry.